

Digital Tools for Stress Management and Employee Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ibadan, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study delves into the effect of digital tools for stress management on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ibadan. Employing a descriptive survey research design, the study captures the opinions, attitudes, and perceptions of 217 employees from Nigerian Brewery Plc, segmented by department and employment cadre. The research utilizes Taro Yamane's formula to determine a sample size of 141 employees, ensuring diverse representation through stratified random sampling. Data collection is conducted via a self-structured questionnaire, which is divided into sections capturing demographic information and responses to research questions on a Likert scale. The questionnaire's reliability is affirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.889. Data analysis is performed using SPSS version 23, employing descriptive statistics, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square tests at a 0.05 significance level. The results reveal a chi-square value (X^2) of 19.74 and a p-value of less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant association between the use of digital tools for stress management and improved employee performance. Further, the chi-square value (X^2) of 91.161 and a p-value of less than 0.05 suggest a significant correlation between the usability of these tools and performance enhancement. Additionally, a chi-square value (X^2) of 68.31 with a p-value of less than 0.05 underscores the perceived usefulness of digital tools as a crucial element in performance improvement. The study concludes that user-friendly and effective digital tools are integral to their successful adoption in the workplace. Recommendations include the integration of digital tools into health and wellness programs, provision of training and support, continuous evaluation of tool effectiveness, encouragement of further research, customization of digital tools, addressing potential adoption barriers, and promoting awareness of the benefits of digital stress management tools. These measures are anticipated to lead to better stress management and enhanced employee performance.

Keywords: Digital tools, Employee performance, Small and medium enterprises, Stress management, Work-life balance

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1 Introduction

Employee performance is a critical factor in organizational success. However, it is often compromised by stress, which can lead to decreased productivity, increased absenteeism,

and higher turnover rates. In the digital age, organizations are turning to innovative tools for stress management to enhance employee performance.

employee performance is intricately linked to stress levels. By prioritizing stress management strategies, organizations can cultivate a thriving workforce that propels them towards success. When organizations invest in digital tools for stress management for their employees, they are not just addressing a personal well-being concern but also strategically aligning with organizational success. As noted by Ganster and Rosen (2013), employee performance stands as a linchpin in achieving organizational goals. However, stress, if left unaddressed, can pose a substantial threat to this performance. In today's fast-paced work environment, stress is an ever-present concern. It affects not only the well-being of employees but also the overall performance of organizations. The World Health Organization has recognized workplace stress as a global epidemic, and it is imperative that organizations address this issue head-on (Oyedokun & Micah, 2019).

The negative impact of stress on employee performance manifests in various ways. Firstly, stress can lead to decreased productivity as individuals find it challenging to focus and maintain concentration amidst heightened stress levels. Tasks that would typically be completed efficiently may take longer to accomplish, or errors may occur due to cognitive impairments associated with stress (McEwen, 2017; Taiwo & Oyedokun, 2022).

Moreover, stress often contributes to absenteeism, where employees may opt to take sick leave or mental health days to cope with or recuperate from overwhelming stressors. This absence not only affects individual productivity but also disrupts team dynamics and workflow, potentially leading to delays in project timelines or increased workloads for remaining team members (Allen et al., 2017). Furthermore, chronic stress can escalate turnover rates within organizations. Employees experiencing high levels of stress may feel disillusioned or burnt out, prompting them to seek alternative employment opportunities where they perceive a better work-life balance or less stressful environment (Schaufeli & Taris, 2014). High turnover rates not only result in the loss of talent but also incur significant recruitment and training costs for the organization.

Conversely, implementing effective stress management strategies, such as providing access to digital tools tailored for stress relief and relaxation, can yield positive outcomes for both employee well-being and organizational performance. By offering employees resources to mitigate stress, organizations empower them to better cope with work-related pressures and maintain optimal performance levels.

Digital tools for stress management can include applications for mindfulness and meditation, stress tracking and management platforms, virtual wellness sessions, and mental health resources. These tools enable employees to proactively manage their stress levels, cultivate resilience, and foster a healthier work-life balance. Research has shown that work-related stress can lead to severe disorders such as depression, musculoskeletal conditions, and coronary artery disease. Digital tools for stress management, such as guided internet-based stress management training (iSMT), have emerged as effective solutions to this problem. These tools offer the flexibility and accessibility that traditional in-person group-based stress management training (gSMT) may lack. Studies comparing the effectiveness of iSMT and gSMT have found that digital interventions can be just as effective, if not more so, in reducing stress and improving employee performance. Furthermore, digital tools can be cost-effective and have the potential to reach a wider audience within the working population. As employees experience reduced stress levels and enhanced well-being through the utilization of these digital tools, they are likely to exhibit improved job satisfaction, engagement, and commitment to their roles (Hassard et al., 2018). This, in turn, translates into higher levels of productivity, as employees are better equipped to perform their tasks efficiently and effectively. Furthermore, a supportive organizational culture that prioritizes employee well-being and provides access to digital tools for stress management can strengthen employee loyalty and retention. Employees are more inclined to remain with organizations that demonstrate a genuine concern for their welfare and offer resources to support their mental and emotional health needs (Ogundajo, Odunayo, Osunsusi, Desi, & Oyedokun, 2023).

In essence, the integration of digital tools for stress management into organizational practices not only fosters a healthier and more resilient workforce but also contributes to enhanced employee performance, reduced absenteeism, and lower turnover rates. As organizations recognize the intrinsic link between employee well-being and organizational success, investing in stress management initiatives becomes imperative for long-term sustainability and competitiveness in today's dynamic business landscape.

Statement of the Problem

Organizations prioritize employee well-being and proactively implement strategies to mitigate workplace stress. This includes providing access to digital tools tailored for stress management, fostering a supportive work environment, and promoting a healthy work-life

balance. In such organizations, employees feel valued, supported, and empowered to manage their stress levels effectively, resulting in enhanced job satisfaction, productivity, and overall organizational performance. However, the current reality often diverges from this ideal. Many organizations, including Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ibadan, Nigeria, may lack comprehensive stress management initiatives and fail to leverage digital tools to support employee well-being (Mokalapa, Oyedokun, & Fowokan, 2024). Consequently, employees may experience high levels of stress, which can adversely affect their performance, job satisfaction, and overall quality of life. The failure to address workplace stress effectively poses several consequences for both employees and organizations. Firstly, elevated stress levels among employees can lead to decreased productivity, absenteeism, and turnover, as outlined by Ganster and Rosen (2013). This, in turn, impacts organizational performance, profitability, and competitiveness in the market. Moreover, chronic stress can detrimentally affect employee mental and physical health, contributing to increased healthcare costs and decreased morale within the workforce.

Prior research has explored the relationship between workplace stress, employee well-being, and organizational performance. However, there is a gap in the literature concerning the specific context of SMEs in Ibadan and their utilization of digital tools for stress management. While larger corporations may have resources to invest in comprehensive well-being programs, SMEs often face resource constraints and may overlook the importance of addressing employee stress systematically. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the impact of digital tools for stress management on employee performance within SMEs in Ibadan. By conducting a thorough investigation into the current practices, challenges, and opportunities related to stress management in SMEs, the study seeks to provide actionable insights for practitioners and policymakers. Specifically, the research will explore the effectiveness of various digital tools, identify barriers to implementation, and offer recommendations for enhancing stress management initiatives in SMEs.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the influence of digital tools for stress management on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The Specific objectives are to:

1. identify how Digital Tools Utilized for Stress Management affect Employee Performance.

2. examine the influence of perceived ease of use of Digital Tools for Stress Management on Employee Performance.
3. find out the influence of perceived effectiveness of Digital Tools for Stress Management on Employee Performance.

2 Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Impact on Employee Performance

The literature suggests that digital stress management tools can lead to improvements in employee performance by reducing perceived stress levels and enhancing resilience. Research indicates that the utilization of digital stress management tools can significantly impact employee performance within organizations. By mitigating perceived stress levels and bolstering resilience, these tools play a pivotal role in enhancing productivity and job satisfaction among employees (Smith & Segal, 2020). This effect is particularly pertinent in high-stress professions where the ability to manage stress effectively is paramount for maintaining optimal performance and well-being (Hammen et al., 2017; Oyedokun & Taiwo, 2022). A study by Hammen et al. (2017) found that employees who actively engaged with digital stress management tools reported lower levels of stress and higher levels of job satisfaction compared to their counterparts who did not utilize such tools. The ability of these tools to provide accessible and personalized stress management resources empowers employees to address stressors more effectively, thereby improving their overall performance and resilience in demanding work environments. Furthermore, the literature suggests that reduced stress levels resulting from the use of digital tools for stress management can lead to fewer instances of burnout and absenteeism among employees (Cavanagh et al., 2018). This, in turn, contributes to higher levels of employee engagement, retention, and organizational commitment, ultimately positively impacting organizational performance metrics such as productivity, profitability, and employee morale (Hassard et al., 2018).

Digital Tools for Stress Management

Digital tools for stress management encompass a diverse array of technological solutions, ranging from mobile applications and online platforms to wearable devices equipped with sensors that monitor physiological indicators of stress (Huckins et al., 2020; Bello & Oyedokun, 2023). These tools are purposefully designed to offer users convenient access to a

wide range of stress-reduction techniques and resources, including but not limited to mindfulness exercises, relaxation techniques, breathing exercises, and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) modules (Mani et al., 2015).

Mobile applications represent one of the most prevalent forms of digital interventions for stress management, with a plethora of options available across various app stores. These applications typically offer features such as guided meditation sessions, stress tracking functionalities, mood monitoring, and personalized recommendations based on user preferences and feedback (Huberty et al., 2019; Oyedokun & Bello, 2020)

Online platforms dedicated to stress management provide users with access to comprehensive resources, including educational materials, self-help modules, and interactive tools for managing stress and improving mental well-being (Richards & Richardson, 2012; Oyedokun & Amoo, 2023). These platforms often incorporate evidence-based techniques derived from fields such as psychology, neuroscience, and behavioral science to deliver effective interventions tailored to individual needs.

Wearable devices equipped with biofeedback sensors enable real-time monitoring of physiological parameters associated with stress, such as heart rate variability (HRV), skin conductance, and electrodermal activity (EDA) (Russo et al., 2015). By providing users with immediate feedback on their stress levels, these devices empower individuals to recognize and manage stress more effectively, often through biofeedback training and relaxation exercises.

Effectiveness and Implementation

Numerous studies have underscored the effectiveness of digital tools in alleviating symptoms associated with stress, depression, and anxiety, all of which constitute substantial contributors to the global burden of disease (Firth et al., 2017; Ilemona, Nwite, & Oyedokun, 2019). Digital interventions, including mobile applications, online platforms, and wearable devices, have demonstrated efficacy in delivering evidence-based techniques such as mindfulness, cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), and relaxation exercises to users, leading to significant reductions in psychological distress and improvements in overall mental well-being (Firth et al., 2017; Mani et al., 2015).

For instance, a meta-analysis by Firth et al. (2017) found that digital interventions targeting mental health conditions, including stress, depression, and anxiety, yielded moderate to large effect sizes in reducing symptom severity compared to control conditions. These findings highlight the potential of digital tools as scalable and cost-effective solutions for addressing mental health challenges on a global scale.

In the workplace context, the implementation of digital tools for stress management has shown promise in enhancing employee resilience, mental health literacy, and coping strategies (Joyce et al., 2018; Oyedekun, Naburgi, & Haruna 2020). By providing employees with accessible resources and support mechanisms, organizations can empower individuals to proactively manage stress, mitigate psychological distress, and build resilience in the face of workplace challenges (Joyce et al., 2018; Ricciardi et al., 2018).

Research by Ricciardi et al. (2018) demonstrated the positive impact of implementing digital stress management interventions in organizational settings. Through targeted interventions delivered via mobile applications and online platforms, employees reported improvements in stress management skills, coping strategies, and overall well-being. Moreover, these interventions contributed to a reduction in absenteeism, turnover intentions, and healthcare costs, highlighting the potential economic benefits of investing in employee mental health and well-being initiatives (Ricciardi et al., 2018; Oyedokun & Muhammad, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

Studying the impact of digital tools for stress management on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ibadan necessitates a theoretical framework that integrates insights from organizational behavior, psychology, and technology adoption literature. One such framework combines the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

The JD-R Model, as proposed by Bakker and Demerouti (2017), suggests that both job demands (like workload and time pressure) and job resources (such as social support and autonomy) influence employee well-being and performance. In the context of SMEs in Ibadan, digital tools for stress management act as job resources, aiding employees in coping with and alleviating the demands of their work environment. According to this model, the availability and utilization of digital tools can lead to a reduction in stress levels and an

enhancement in performance by providing employees with the necessary support to effectively manage job demands.

Complementing the JD-R Model, the TAM, developed by Davis in 1989, emphasizes the role of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness in determining the adoption and utilization of technology by individuals. Within the realm of digital tools for stress management, employees' perceptions of the ease of use and effectiveness of these tools significantly impact their willingness to integrate them into their daily routines. Understanding employees' attitudes and beliefs towards digital tools can thus predict their adoption behavior and subsequently influence stress management and performance within SMEs in Ibadan.

3 Methodology

This chapter outlines the systematic procedures employed in the study, focusing on the research design, target population, sampling methods, research instruments, and data analysis techniques, along with ethical considerations. A descriptive survey research design is utilized to capture individual opinions, attitudes, and perceptions within their natural settings. This approach is beneficial for describing variables and factual information as they exist, thereby clarifying the operational effects of the variables and the relationships between them. The study encompasses all 217 employees of Nigerian Brewery Plc in Ibadan, Oyo state, segmented by department and employment cadre. The company's selection was based on its location and accessibility. Sampling Technique Using Taro Yamale's formula. The formula is $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$, with a 5% error tolerance, the sample size is determined to be 141 employees. Stratified random sampling ensures representation across different job cadres. Random samples were drawn from each group to ensure representation across senior management, middle supervision, and lower employee cadres. Primary data is collected through a self-structured questionnaire, divided into two sections: demographic information and structured items related to the research questions, using a Likert scale for responses. Reliability is tested by administering the questionnaire to a group outside the sample size, aiming for consistent results that affirm the instrument's accuracy with cronbach Alpha of 0.889. Thus, questionnaires are distributed and collected by the researcher to guarantee prompt and accurate data retrieval. Data is analyzed using descriptive statistics, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Chi-square, and correlation tests at a 0.05 significance level, with SPSS version 23 ensuring precise data analysis.

4 Results and Discussion of Findings

Presentation of Demographic Data

Table 1: Distribution of Demographic Data

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	83	65.9
	Female	43	34.1
	Total	126	100.0
Department	Senior Management Cadre	10	7.09
	Middle supervision Cadre	34	24.1
	Lower Employee Cadre	97	68.8
	Total	126	100.0
Qualifications	Diploma	20	15.9
	Bachelor	40	31.7
	Masters	66	52.4
	Total	126	100.0
Years of Experience	1-5	13	10.3
	6-10	27	21.4
	11-15	40	31.7
	16& above	46	36.5
	Total	126	100.0

Table 1 showed that 126 respondents participated in the study. The gender distribution shows that 83 (65.9%) of the respondents were female while (43) 34.1% of the remaining respondents were male. department distribution shows that 10 (7.092%) of the respondents were Senior Managers, 34 (24.3%) of the respondents were supervisors, while remaining 97 (68.8%) of the respondents were Lower Employees. Qualification distribution shows that 20 (15.9%) of the respondents had diploma qualification, 40 (31.7%) of the respondents had bachelor qualification, 66 (52.4%) of the respondents were master's holders. Distribution of years of experience show that 13 (10.3%) of the employees have been in the organization for up to 1-5 years, 27 (21.4%) of the employees have been in the organization for up to 6-10 years, 40 (31.7%) of the employees have been in the organization for up to 11-15 years, 46 (36.5%) of the employees have been in the organization for up to 16 and above years.

(21.4%)of the employees have been in the organization for up to 11-15 years and 27 (21.4%)of the employees have been in the organization for up to46 (36.5)

Table 2: Response Rate

Questionnaires	Frequency	Percent
Administered	126	87.5
Return administered	18	12.5
Total	141	100.0

Analysis of Research Objectives

Objective one: identify how Digital Tools Utilized for Stress Management affect Employee Performance

Table 3: Level of how Digital Tools Utilized for Stress Management affect Employee Performance

			Employee Performance			Total	Chi-Square Tests	
			strongly agree	agree	Disagree		X ²	p-value
Digital Tools Utilized for Stress Management	strongly agree	Count	30	12	0	42		
		% within	68.2%	42.9%	0.0%	56.8%		
	Agree	Count	14	14	2	30		
		% within	31.8%	50.0%	100.0%	40.5%	19.74 ^a	.048
	Disagree	Count	0	2	0	2		
		% within	0.0%	7.1%	0.0%	2.7%		
Total		Count	44	28	2	74		
		% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

The information provided in Table 3 clearly demonstrates the significant influence that digital stress management tools have on employee performance. The data indicates a high level of consensus among the participants, with a substantial majority of exactly 56.8% agreeing—either strongly or simply—that these digital tools are good for improving work performance. Upon closer examination of the data, we notice a notable statistic: 68.2% of the participants who expressed a 'strongly agree' response make up the largest group within this category, showing a significant belief in the usefulness of these digital interventions. In

contrast, there is very little dissent, with only 2.7% voicing disagreement, indicating a strong consensus on the favorable impact of these instruments. The statistical analysis conducted in this study revealed that the Chi-Square Tests yielded a chi-square value (X^2) of 19.74 and a p-value of less than 0.05. Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, which is the chosen level of significance, it can be inferred that there is a statistically significant association between the utilization of digital tools for stress management and the subsequent improvement in employee performance. The statistical analysis strongly supports the perception that digital tools for stress management are useful in enhancing employee performance among the studied population. Therefore, the effectiveness of these digital tools in managing stress is crucial for enhancing workplace productivity and well-being.

Objective Two: influence of perceived ease of use of Digital Tools for Stress Management on Employee Performance,

Table 4 Influence of Perceived Ease of use of Digital Tools for Stress Management on Employee Performance

		Employee Performance			Total	Chi-Square Tests	
		strongly agree	Agree	Disagree		X ²	P-value
perceived ease of use of Digital Tools for Stress Management	strongly agree	Count	34	8	0	42	91.161 .000
		% within	77.3%	28.6%	0.0%	56.8%	
Agree		Count	10	20	0	30	
		% within	22.7%	71.4%	0.0%	40.5%	
Disagree		Count	0	0	2	2	
		% within	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	2.7%	
Total		Count	44	28	2	74	
		% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table 4 presents a narrative that effectively conveys the perceived user-friendliness of digital tools for managing stress and their cumulative impact on worker productivity. The data shown on the page indicates that a significant majority, specifically 56.8%, are in agreement, either strongly or moderately, that the ease of use of these instruments has a beneficial effect

on their performance. The 77.3% who 'strongly agree' receive the most attention, highlighting the significance of user-friendly digital tools in managing workplace well-being. The lack of dispute in the 'agree' category, with a significant 71.4%, and the absence of any disagreement in the 'strongly agree' and 'agree' categories, highlight the unanimity about the effectiveness of these instruments. The statistical composition reaches its climax with The Chi-Square Tests findings indicate that the chi-square value (X^2) is 91.161, and the p-value is less than 0.05. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the significance level is significant. This statistically significant finding conclusively indicates a significant correlation between the usability of digital tools for stress management and the improvement of employee performance. Hence, user-friendly digital solutions play a crucial role in optimizing employee performance, thereby improving productivity and fostering a harmonious work environment.

Objective Three: influence of perceived effectiveness of Digital Tools for Stress Management on Employee Performance,

Table 5 Influence of Perceived Effectiveness of Digital Tools for Stress Management on Employee Performance

			Employee Performance			Total	Chi-Square Tests	
			strongly agree	Agree	Disagree		X ²	p-value
perceived effectiveness of Digital Tools for Stress Management	strongly	Count	24	10	0	34	68.31	.000
	agree	% within	54.5%	35.7%	0.0%	45.9%		
	Agree	Count	20	16	0	36		
		% within	45.5%	57.1%	0.0%	48.6%		
	Disagree	Count	0	2	0	2		
		% within	0.0%	7.1%	0.0%	2.7%		
Disagree	Count	0	0	2	2			
	% within	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	2.7%			
Total	Count	44	28	2	74			
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

The statistical analysis shown in Table 5 highlights the significant impact of the perceived effectiveness of digital tools for stress management on employee performance. The data reveals a clear pattern, with 45.9% of the respondents expressing a strong agreement and

48.6% expressing agreement with the effectiveness of these digital tools. This highlights the widespread good acceptance of these technical assistance. With 54.5% of the respondents strongly agreeing, who play the role of protagonists in this story, the storyline becomes more complex as they confirm the considerable influence of these technologies. On the other hand, the respondents who agree, comprising 57.1% of the total, endorse the narrative, so strengthening the idea that the simplicity of use is a crucial element in the effective implementation of stress management methods. The lack of disagreement in the 'strongly agree' and 'agree' categories, contrasted with the unequivocal disagreement among the 2.7% who 'disagree', adds an unexpected element to the story, emphasizing the almost universal acknowledgment of the instruments' efficacy. The Chi-Square Tests findings indicate that the chi-square value (X^2) is 68.31 and the p-value is less than 0.05. Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, which is the chosen level of significance, we can infer that there is a statistically significant association between the perceived usefulness of digital tools and the improvement of employee performance. Therefore, data confirms that the perceived efficacy of digital tools for stress management is a crucial element in enhancing employee performance inside the enterprise.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of objectives of this study corroborate with a burgeoning body of research highlighting the pivotal role of digital tools in stress management and their consequential impact on employee performance. Our statistical analysis resonates with recent literature, indicating that digital interventions are effective not only in managing stress but also in enhancing workplace productivity and employee well-being. For instance, a study published in *Frontiers in Digital Health* delves into the utilization, effectiveness, and implementation of digital tools for relaxation and stress management, accentuating their potential to augment mental health interventions (Smith & Segal, 2020). Similarly, an editorial in the same journal underscores the escalating prevalence of stress, depression, and anxiety as major contributors to the global burden of disease, emphasizing the appeal of digital tools as vehicles for disseminating evidence-based interventions (Jones et al., 2019). Furthermore, a study protocol outlined in *BMC Public Health* compares the efficacy of guided internet-based stress management training with established, in-person group training among employees, suggesting that digital interventions can rival, if not surpass, traditional methods in alleviating stress and enhancing employee performance (Richards & Richardson, 2012). These studies collectively validate the findings of our research, indicating that the perceived

ease of use and effectiveness of digital tools for stress management significantly influence employee performance. Integrating such tools into the workplace could therefore represent a strategic initiative for organizations striving to cultivate a healthier, more productive workforce.

The results of Objective two underscore a notable correlation between the usability of digital tools for stress management and the enhancement of employee performance, echoing findings from several pertinent studies. These studies collectively underscore the significance of user-friendly digital solutions in bolstering workplace productivity and fostering a conducive work environment.

For instance, research published in *Frontiers in Digital Health* discusses the efficacy of digital tools for relaxation and stress management, highlighting the increasing adoption of user-friendly digital interventions in mental health care due to their accessibility and ease of use (Smith & Segal, 2020). Similarly, a study from the *Journal of Medical Internet Research* reinforces this notion, suggesting that the acceptability and usability of digital health interventions play a pivotal role in improving outcomes for individuals with depression, anxiety, and somatoform disorders (Jones et al., 2019). Furthermore, an article from MDPI underscores that participants engaging with digital stress management interventions, whether through face-to-face or online modalities, exhibited significantly reduced perceived stress and emotional exhaustion, alongside increased work engagement (Richards & Richardson, 2012). This underscores the premise that the ease of use of digital tools can profoundly impact their efficacy in mitigating stress and enhancing employee performance. Our study's findings align with the broader research landscape, consistently highlighting the usability of digital tools for stress management as a critical determinant in optimizing employee performance. By integrating user-friendly digital solutions into the workplace, organizations can not only bolster productivity but also foster the well-being and satisfaction of their employees.

The findings from Objective three, which unveil a statistically significant correlation between the perceived usefulness of digital tools for stress management and the enhancement of employee performance, resonate throughout the broader research landscape. This correlation holds paramount importance for enterprises aiming to bolster productivity and employee well-being through the adoption of such tools. For example, a study published in *BMC Emergency Medicine* delves into the digital stressors and resources perceived by emergency physicians and their associations with digital stress perception, mental health, job

satisfaction, and work engagement (Smith & Segal, 2020). The study underscores the persistence of digital stressors and resources and their potential impact on health and work-related outcomes, emphasizing the necessity for preventive measures to address technology-related stressors.

Similarly, a qualitative systematic review published in BMC Health Services Research aims to identify barriers and facilitators to the implementation of digital technologies in mental healthcare systems (Jones et al., 2019). The review suggests that while challenges exist, such as the perception of digital technologies as impersonal tools, facilitators like person-centered approaches and evidence-based training for providers can aid in the successful integration of digital health interventions.

Moreover, an editorial in *Frontiers in Digital Health* discusses the utilization, effectiveness, and implementation of digital tools for relaxation and stress management, highlighting their potential to cultivate resilience and mitigate stress among medical students (Richards & Richardson, 2012). These studies corroborate our findings by affirming that the perceived effectiveness of digital tools is pivotal in their successful adoption and subsequent positive impact on employee performance. Additionally, they underscore the importance of addressing the multifaceted nature of barriers and facilitators in the implementation of such technologies. By comprehending and tackling these factors, enterprises can effectively harness digital tools for stress management to elevate employee performance and overall organizational productivity.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study has established a significant correlation between the use of digital tools for stress management and the enhancement of employee performance. The perceived ease of use and effectiveness of these tools are crucial factors that contribute to their successful adoption in the workplace. The findings suggest that when employees find digital tools user-friendly and effective, they are more likely to incorporate them into their daily routines, leading to improved stress management and, consequently, better performance.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made to organizations and researchers:

1. **Integration of Digital Tools:** Organizations should integrate user-friendly digital tools for stress management into their health and wellness programs to improve employee performance and well-being.
2. **Training and Support:** Provide training and ongoing support to employees to ensure they can fully utilize these digital tools effectively.
3. **Continuous Evaluation:** Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of the digital tools in place to ensure they meet the changing needs of the employees and the organization.
4. **Further Research:** Researchers should conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of digital tools for stress management on employee performance.
5. **Customization and Personalization:** Develop and implement digital tools that can be customized and personalized to fit the individual needs of employees.
6. **Addressing Barriers:** Identify and address potential barriers to the adoption of digital tools, such as concerns about privacy and data security.
7. **Promoting Awareness:** Increase awareness among employees about the benefits of using digital tools for stress management.

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